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Open Data Management Plan

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PRO	Technical/economic progress report (internal work package reports indicating work status)	
DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
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Executive Summary

FishEUTrust aims to collect, manage, and utilize data related to fish and shellfish. This data encompasses a wide range of information, including the quality of both wild and farmed fish and shellfish, regulatory and labelling standards, and consumer acceptance. Some of this data was sourced from previous projects and partners' activities, but the majority has been collected through ongoing FishEUTrust initiatives.

The FishEUTrust Data Management Plan (DMP) is a core document addressing all open internal research data management activities in FishEUTrust. This is a working document that complies with the Horizon Europe template for DMP. It outlines data management strategies for satisfying the requirements for research data management in Horizon Europe.

1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

At the beginning of the project, the FishEUTrust partners contributed with research and industrial (e.g., OXY) data on fish composition and other characteristics collected in previous projects (e.g., Realmed, SeeFoodTomorrow etc.). During the project, additional data on fish has been generated covering different aspects (i.e., chemical/environmental, economic, social etc.). The data collected so far is detailed in Table 1, which is dynamically updated on the project's [NextCloud portal](#).

The data are heterogenous, meaning that they are of different types and formats. An objective of the project is to develop various software solutions (such as web services, Machine learning pipelines and other workflows for data analysis) for re-using heterogeneous data (i.e., data of different types and formats) provided from different data sources. The purpose of linking and analysing such data using advanced computer methods (Machine learning, Natural language processing etc., described in detail in D4.3) is to find answers on open research questions. This might be useful for researchers as well as for other FishEUTrust stakeholders (like fish industry, especially SMEs, policy makers etc.). A comprehensive list of FishEUTrust stakeholders has been prepared by ABT (in Task 1.1 to be published in D1.2).

Table 1. Data summary - draft

Partner	Existing data	Data types	Data formats	Utility for Objectives	Data size	Data origin	Data utility outside the project
JSI (1)	Composition data for fish	Isotope data, elemental composition data, fatty acids in fish and mussels	Semi-structured (XML)	Identification of fish origin and production type (wild / farmed)	X data points for Y different fishes	RealMed, Promedlife / FishEUTrust	Identification of fish origin and production type (wild / farmed)
IPMA (2)	Composition data for fish	Lipidomic data	Semi-Structured (XML)	Identification of production type (wild / farmed)	X data points for Y different fishes	FishEUTrust	Identification of production type (wild / farmed)
UNIBO (3)	Results of household survey on consumers from Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia attitudes and choices related to fish products and aquaculture	Survey data (at household level)	SPSS file	Identification of characteristics and behaviours of consumers in 3 countries, Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia, representative of the Northern, Mediterranean, and Central regions of Europe	388 kb	FishEUTrust	Identification of consumers characteristics, attitudes, and choices related to aquaculture and aquaculture products
EuroFISH (4)						FishEUTrust	
UNIFI (5) - Duccio	Composition data for fish,	Metagenome data	Semi-structured (XML)	Identification of fish origin and production type (wild / farmed)	X data points for Y different fishes	? / FishEUTrust	Identification of fish origin and production type (wild / farmed)
UNIFI (5) - Giovanna	Data on toxins in mussels	Sensor data					
UMF (6)	Data on biological and chemical contaminants in fish	Sensor data	Semi-structured (XML)	Identification of contaminants in fish		? / FishEUTrust	Identification of contaminants in fish
DTU (7)	Dietary health impacts and environmental impacts for 18 impact categories for 5800 food items	Environmental impacts data	Semi-structured (Excel)	Ecological footprint calculation	X data points for Y different scenarios	Pilot cases from Denmark and Portugal, and from literature / FishEUTrust	Ecological footprint calculation
BTU CS (9)	Data on fish freshness	Instrumental analysis data	Semi-structured (XML)	Quantification of the fish freshness, i.e., the time since the fish was caught		FishEUTrust	Quantification of the fish freshness, i.e., the time since the fish was caught

				for particular storage conditions			for particular storage conditions
NORCE (10)						FishEUTrust	
EuroFIR (11)	Plant-based bioactive compounds		Semi-structured				
	Composition data on food waste streams		Semi-structured (XML)			REFRESH	
	Food composition data		Semi-structured (XML)			EuroFIR	
UNIPD (12)		DNA coding data					
ABT (13)	Data on stakeholders	Publicly available data + survey data	Semi-structured (Excel)	Stakeholder analysis + Survey analysis	500	FishEUTrust	Business development
REDINN (14)						FishEUTrust	
BELIT (15)	/					FishEUTrust	
CETGA (18)						FishEUTrust	
DIGITALSMART (18)	IoT data on fish	pH, T, DO, ORP, EC, GPS, QR code	Structured data (JSON)	Digital passport	5kb per measurement (measurement resolution is set to 15 minutes, could be adjusted)	Pilot case from Montenegro / FishEUTrust	Water quality monitoring, Cold storage transport monitoring, Batch traceability
BUGENVILA (20)	Details about seafood recipes	Seafood recipes	Unstructured (textual data)	Studying how consumers are able to distinguish between wild and farmed fish once prepared as dish	Few tens	Bugenvila	/
OXY (20)	Composition on water matrix, fish and feed	Quantitative content automatic measured with digital sensors. Manual registered data on growth, mortalities, medication etc.	Semi-structured (XML)	Digital passport through Cobália (production management software)	Data stored and available in 'the cloud'	FishEUTrust/fish farm & hatchery in DK	Original data is owned by the fish farms - and as such not available for public use

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Some data provided by project partners is already identified with persistent identifiers, such as the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and similar. For example, datasets provided through the the H2020 project Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud)¹ have assigned identifiers since they are stored in Zenodo. Data in a form of scientific papers (provided by JSI, UNIBO, UNIPD, UNIFI) is identified by DOI.

Datasets collected by EuroFIR comply with the CEN/TC387 standard on food data, which specifies various metadata describing data quality. Moreover, data from these datasets have been classified with respect to global systems like LanguaL² and FoodEx2³.

Fish microbiome data gathered by Unifi is already annotated with respect to the FNS-Harmony ontology⁴. This application ontology was developed in FNS-Cloud to describe concepts and entities from the food and nutrition domain.

Isotopic data for fish that collected in the FishEUTrust project are represented using the ISO-FOOD ontology⁵ developed in the FP7 ERA Chair ISO-FOOD project⁶. The ISO-FOOD ontology has been linked with the FNS-Harmony ontology to enable semantic interoperability of FishEUTrust data with data from other food and nutrition domains (in T7.3).

Regarding search keywords, an objective of the FishEUTrust project is to develop a platform where functionality of advanced searching data based on its metadata is being implemented (in WP7).

Metadata has been designed and structured to allow its harvesting and indexing. Experiences from previous projects (e.g., ERA Chair ISO-FOOD, FNS-Cloud, COMFOCUS etc.) have been taken into consideration defining the FishEUTrust metadata model.

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository

¹ <https://www.fns-cloud.eu/>

² <https://www.langual.org/default.asp>

³ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data/data-standardisation>

⁴ <https://github.com/panovp/FNS-Harmony>

⁵ Eftimov, T., Ispirova, G., Potočnik, D., Ogrinc, N., Koroušić Seljak, B. (2019) ISO-FOOD ontology: A formal representation of the knowledge within the domain of isotopes for food science, Food Chemistry 277: 382-390, doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.10.118.

⁶ <http://isofood.eu>

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Each partner stores and archives data in a trusted repository suggested by its institution. However, the project openly accessible outcomes will be deposited in Zenodo⁷, where all meta data is openly available under CC0 licence and all content is openly accessible through open APIs. Zenodo helps researchers to receive credit by making the research results citable and through OpenAIRE integrates them into existing reporting lines to the European Commission and other funding agencies. Citation information is also passed to DataCite and onto the scholarly aggregators.

Apropos appropriate arrangements between the Consortium and Zenodo, the Terms and Conditions made public by Zenodo⁸ do not make necessary to arrive to an arrangement as these Terms and Conditions are public and their acceptance is necessary to use their services.

As stated before, Zenodo provides DOI to all uploaded data, therefore the repository ensures that the data is assigned an identifier and resolves the identifier to a digital object.

Data

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g., patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g., to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

In this stage of the project, we are still discussing which data will be openly available.

According to FishEUTrust Document of Action (DOA), no data embargo is previewed.

All openly accessible data will be available through open APIs. For other data, a data access committee (DAC) will be established to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data. The DAC members will be elected at the next FishEUTrust general assembly. No restriction on the use of openly accessible data exists, apart from giving the appropriate credit to the data creator.

In case FishEUTrust partners need to exchange any sensitive (personal, industrial) data, encrypted tools and safe FTP-solutions provided by their IT-services will be used.

⁷ <https://zenodo.org>

⁸ <https://about.zenodo.org/terms/>

Metadata

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open-source code)?

All meta data deposited in Zenodo will be openly available under CC0 licence. It will contain enough information (including direct link) to enable a user to access the data.

The data will remain available and findable for at least five years after the end of the project. All metadata is guaranteed to remain available also after data is no longer available.

As the case may be, if the used software includes a CITATION.cff file⁹, it will be used as reference. Citation.Cff files have been developed by The Institute for Software Technology of the German Aerospace Center (DLR), The Netherlands eScience Center and The Software Sustainability Institute. It is supported by Github, Zenodo, Zotero.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

FishEUTrust structured data are formatted using popular formats avoiding in all cases vendor lock in problems.

To make FishEUTrust data of different types and formats interoperable, existing application ontologies, like FNS-Harmony and ISO-FOOD, have been linked and used to represent the FishEUTrust knowledge. Both ontologies are already openly published.

In FishEUTrust we are further developing a web-based tool FoodViz¹⁰, which enables mapping of concepts and entities to different semantic resources (such as Hansard corpus, FoodOn, SnomedCT etc.).

⁹ <https://citation-file-format.github.io/>

¹⁰ <http://foodviz.env4health.finki.ukim.mk/#/cafeteria?recipeId=c-10048971>

2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g., readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?

Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

By the end of the project, each dataset will be enriched with documentation to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g., readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.).

Most FishEUTrust data will be made freely available (through Zenodo). We are also discussing ways of sharing data through research infrastructures, like METROFOOD and ELIXIR Europe. In this way, a broader range of scientists and industry will be reached.

All data managed in the project will be licensed using standard reuse licences, in line with the obligations set forth in the Grant Agreement and be handled according to the EU GDPR requirements.

The data provenance will be thoroughly documented following the Dublin Core Model¹¹.

FAIRness of the project outcome data and other outputs in a form of digital objects will be assessed using assessment tools, such as FAIR Data Self-Assessment Tool¹² or DANS-Fairdat¹³. Existing resources (e.g., FAIRshake.cloud¹⁴) have been explored to identify any additional tool that might be relevant for the project.

The FishEUTrust partners are advised to follow the ELIXIR resource [FAIRcookbook](#) aimed for life scientists to help them to make and keep data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

¹¹ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/terms/provenance/>

¹² <https://ardc.edu.au/resource/fair-data-self-assessment-tool/>

¹³ <https://satisfyd.dans.knaw.nl/>

¹⁴ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S240547121930345X?via%3Dihub>

In FishEUTrust both digital as well as physical outputs are being generated. Their compliance with the FAIR principles is managed by their creators and will be documented in further versions of this DMP.

4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g., direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Each partner covers costs for making its data and other research outputs FAIR in FishEUTrust. Costs for making outputs generated by more partners FAIR will be shared or covered by the whole consortium, in case the outputs are of general interest. During the project, these costs will be covered from the project budget. How the costs will be covered after the end of the project, needs to be discussed in the first period of the project. The FishEUTrust partners are advised to use ELIXIR services to estimate the costs of data management, such as:

- [DSW Storage Costs Evaluator](#)
- [UK Data Service Data Management Costing Tool](#)
- [TU Delft Data Management Costing Tool](#)

Barbara Koroušić Seljak (JSI) is in charge of the overall data management in FishEUTrust. A data management committee has been established (partners JSI -N. Ogrinc, B. Koroušić Seljak, EuroFIR - S. Astley, and JdIC – J. de la Cueva).

How long-term preservation will be ensured and what resources are needed to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long) will be discussed as soon as the FishEUTrust data model is defined, which is being done within T7.3 (to be published in D7.3 as part of the FishEUTrust platform specification).

5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Each partner is responsible for implementing all the necessary measures to secure the processing of research data required for the implementation of its project activities. In particular, by taking measures¹⁵, such as:

- To take technical and organisational measures to prevent any unauthorised access to datasets and electronic files, e.g., login restrictions and the use of strong passwords¹⁶;
- To establish clear access rules to their databases (for instance, based on predefined user lists and access rights limitations aiming to disable the possibility to make copies, printing or downloads);
- To organise the processing (also on behalf a project partner) keeping the best possible control of the data ensuring appropriate security safeguards;

¹⁵ <https://www.eui.eu/Documents/ServicesAdmin/DeanOfStudies/ResearchEthics/Guide-Data-Protection-Research.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://blog.avast.com/strong-password-ideas>

- Setting local encrypted storage (e.g., enable the full disk encryption turning data into a form that makes them unintelligible);
- Protecting the data transfer (e.g., using the HTTPS communication over Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) within a connection encrypted by Secure Sockets Layer (SSL).

The aforementioned measures are aligned with the legal provisions of the Consortium Agreement regarding Specific responsibilities regarding data protection (Section 4.4) and Non-disclosure of information (Section 10). However, there are specific legal requirements regarding the processing of personal data, which shall be fulfilled by all project partners according to the applicable EU and national legislation for the protection of personal data. It is important to consider that processing of personal data is not required only during the project implementation but also it may be required for exploitation (post-project) of FishEUTrust. Consequently, project partners shall take all the measures to ensure adequate and effective compliance with the data protection regulations during and after the project. In particular, concerning the notification procedures (i.e., Privacy Policy and Data Processing Agreements) and security measures.

Each partner is individually responsible for the compliance with the legal requirements and provision established in the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁷. During the project, an assessment of GDPR compliance measures will be implemented to verify adequate compliance with the GDPR for the project implementation. The assessment of GDPR compliance measures will be conducted by JSI among the project partners processing personal data required for the project implementation.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Partnering and co-creation are at the heart of FishEUTrust. For the project to be successful, it is key to collect data about participants and stakeholders as well as their ideas, interests and opinions. Partners gather such data using a range of techniques and adhering to the relevant data protection rules (described above in Section 5). Personal data protection is in line with GDPR.

Data collected within FishEUTrust to identify characteristics and behaviours of consumers in 3 countries (Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia), have been processed following the UNIBO data management procedures (Table 2), which includes guidelines for storing consent and regarding data subjects' rights vis-à-vis their data. How long the data will be stored is still an open question, which will be resolved at the next General Assembly meeting.

There is a clear need to make a thorough ethical evaluation of methods applied to generate project results. In FishEUTrust, an interdisciplinary Advisory Board (AB) was set up to support the project implementation. The Board is composed of experts from the following fields: Fish Industries Consortium, Citizen Engagement, Research and Academia. Furthermore, an Ethical Officer has been appointed, Dr. Lada Timotijevic (University of Surrey), who is an external independent Ethics Advisor (more information in D10.2).

FishEUTrust develops also AI-based methods for analysing research data on fish and shellfish (in WP4), which are aligned with the EU Act AI¹⁸ and ethics guidelines for developing trustworthy AI¹⁹.

¹⁷ <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

¹⁸ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20230601STO93804/eu-ai-act-first-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence>

¹⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

There is a special WP10 devoted to Ethics Requirements, led by JSI. Deliverables 10.1, 10.2, 10.3 and 10.4 (M1, M18, M36 and M48) are aimed to analyse any ethical issue raised during the project under the supervision of the external Independent Ethical Advisor.

Project results and future work plans are discussed with the AB at least once in a project year.

7. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

In the next version of the DMP, the information about any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management will be provided in Table 2 (it is being collected by the FishEUTrust partners).

Table 2. Data management procedures

Partner	Procedures
JSI (1)	None formal research data management guidelines at JSI yet
IPMA (2)	None formal research data management guidelines at IPMA yet
UNIBO (3)	https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://www.unibo.it/en/attachments/university-policy-on-research-data-management/%40%40download/file/The-University-Policy-on-research-data-management.pdf&ved=2ahUKewjFoInDta2GAXW6wAIHHVbRBGEQFnoECA4QAQ&usg=AOvVaw0fuPTbAVWJqAQAJCjgINzS
EuroFISH (4)	
UNIFI (5)	https://www.unifi.it/index.php?module=CMpro&func=viewpage&pageid=12570&newlang=en
UMF (6)	
DTU (7)	https://www.dtu.dk/english/research/research-framework/research-data-management
WRG (8)	
BTU CS (9)	
NORCE (10)	
EuroFIR (11)	
UNIPD (12)	
ABT (13)	Privacy & GDPR Compliance - AquaBioTech Group (aquabt.com)
REDINN (14)	
BELIT (15)	
MICRUX (16)	

JdIC (17)	
CETGA (18)	
DIGITALSMART (19)	
BUGENVILA (20)	
OXY (21)	

Conclusions

The Data Management Plan might be modified over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as new data or changes in the consortium policies and the progress of the dissemination and exploitation strategy for each collected or generated dataset.

